

Japa' Syndrome in Nigerian Tertiary Institutions

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Abstract:

Recently, tertiary institutions in Nigeria are plagued with a major problem called Japa' syndrome which simply mean mass exodus of professionals from Nigeria to other part of developed countries for greener pasture. Daily, academic staff and non-academic staff of Nigerian tertiary institutions are moving out of the country for a better placement in the developed countries. This paper discuss the effects of Japa' syndrome on the tertiary institutions development and measures to tackle the Japa' syndrome across the tertiary institutions. Depending on online publications and print materials collected from internet and print resources. The paper identified factors responsible for Japa' syndrome among academic staff of tertiary institutions to includes; poor salaries, poor work condition, economic hardship, insecurity problems in Nigeria, inadequate infrastructure facilities and bad leadership. On the effects of Japa' syndrome on the tertiary institutions development, the paper listed shortage of academic staff, poor quality of tertiary institutions, capital flight and slowing down tertiary institutions development. On measures to tackle Japa' syndrome among academic staff of tertiary institutions in Nigeria, adequate funding, upward review of academic staff salaries and payment of withheld salaries and earned allowances, provision of modern infrastructure facilities, good and governance and provision of adequate security across the country.

Keywords: Japa' Syndrome, tertiary institutions.

Introduction

The Chairman of Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU), University of Lagos (UNILAG), chapter Kayode Adebayo told Sunday Independent that the institution has suffered the Japa syndrome as some of the faculty members have left the system while others are still contemplating the option to seek greener pastures abroad as reported by (Oyeniran, 2023). ‘Japa’ – a Yoruba word meaning “to run, flee or escape” – symbolizes the aspirations of Nigerians who aspire to leave the country in pursuit of greener pastures (Agbajileke, 2023). The ‘Japa’ syndrome, which has been on for a while now has brought nightmares to the Nigerian university system. “This is because of the high migration of lecturers to Europe, America, Asia, and even to some African countries according to Oyesoji Aremu (2023). Japa, a Yoruba locution which means to leave for greener pastures, is still consistently running errands in the frustrated minds of Nigerian youths. Not long ago, another batch of close friends left the shores of Nigeria to Brampton, Ontario, Canada. Sadly, they left because they can no longer bear the distressing issues we have always fussed about; issues of neglect and oppressive government, calling the bluff of the weak citizens and treating them with disdain (Oludotun, 2023).. From the above, ‘Japa’ – a Yoruba word meaning “to run, flee or escape” – implies an economic and social movement of professional, students and ordinary Nigerians to foreign land in seeking for a better job opportunities and quality education. Japa’ can also be described as mass migration of Nigerians from home country to other part of the developed countries for greener pasture.

Elazeh (2023) concluded that unless something drastic, and perhaps radical too, is done, we may wake up one day to see that the only persons left in the country are politicians, senior civil servants who have unrestrained access to the public coffers and persons who have no means of leaving the country. Today, Nigerian youths, most of whom have graduated from tertiary institutions, are ready to take all sorts of risks just to travel to the western countries in search of the proverbial greener pasture. Agbajileke, (2023) maintained that no profession is spared in the ‘Japa’ syndrome, as medical personnel, legal practitioners, bankers, academics, computer geeks, engineers, skilled and unskilled workers, among others leave the country in droves to pursue opportunities elsewhere.

Recently, the International Organisation for Migration (IOM), revealed that no fewer than 260,000 Nigerians approached it for assistance to leave the country this year, suggesting clearly that the nation is standing on the proverbial time-bomb. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), no fewer than 2,000 Nigerian doctors leave the country annually to either the United States of America, United Kingdom or Canada. The mind-boggling statistics about exodus of health workers where it is estimated that no fewer than 75,000 nurses and midwives left the country in the last five years is benumbing (Elazeh 2023). Available records indicate that Nigeria lost over 9,000 medical doctors to these three countries between 2016 and 2018, with yet another report disclosing that no fewer than 727 medical doctors trained in Nigeria relocated to the UK alone in six months, between December 2021 and May 2022 (Elazeh 2023). Painting a gloomy picture of the Japa situation in the country, the President of the Faculty of Public Health and Community Medicine, National Postgraduate Medical College of Nigeria, Professor Akinsanya Osibogun, disclosed that 50 percent of graduate doctors have left Nigeria as reported by (Oyeniran 2023).

A recent survey from the Nigeria Social Cohesion Survey revealed that seven out of 10 Nigerians are willing to relocate to other countries for various reasons, with a good number of them recording success. Today, there is still the increasing rate of an emerging urge to leave Nigeria by the old and the young. Now, the current net Nigeria migration rate is -0.273 per 1000 population, indicating that more people are emigrating from the country. It's depressing that Nigeria is currently sinking deep in brain drain, and it probably needs a call for emergency as reported by (Oludotun, 2023).

In the tertiary education sub-sector, the Japa syndrome has affected almost all aspects of the tertiary institutions. Report by Waheed (2023) and politics digest (2023) disclosed that the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) raised the alarm that most departments in Nigeria's public universities were short-staffed due to the resignation of lecturers in search of greener pastures due Japa syndrome. It is imperative to discuss the implication of Japa syndrome on management of tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

This paper is anchored on Frederick Herzberg, two factor theory of 1959, a behavioural scientist who proposed the two-factor theory or the motivator-hygiene theory. According to Herzberg, there are some job factors that result in satisfaction while there are other job factors that prevent dissatisfaction. According to Herzberg, the opposite of "Satisfaction" is "No satisfaction" and the opposite of "Dissatisfaction" is "No Dissatisfaction".

1. Hygiene factors- Hygiene factors are those job factors which are essential for existence of motivation at workplace. These do not lead to positive satisfaction for long-term. But if these factors are absent/if these factors are non-existent at workplace, then they lead to dissatisfaction.

In other words, hygiene factors are those factors which when adequate/reasonable in a job, pacify the employees and do not make them dissatisfied. These factors are extrinsic to work.

Hygiene factors are also called as **dissatisfiers or maintenance factors** as they are required to avoid dissatisfaction. These factors describe the job environment/scenario. The hygiene factors symbolized the physiological needs which the individuals wanted and expected to be fulfilled.

Hygiene factors include:

a) Pay: The pay or salary structure should be appropriate and reasonable. It must be equal and competitive to those in the same industry in the same domain.

b) Company Policies and administrative policies: The company policies should not be too rigid. They should be fair and clear. It should include flexible working hours, dress code, breaks, vacation, etc.

c) Fringe benefits: The employees should be offered health care plans (medicclaim), benefits for the family members, employee help programmes, etc.

d) Physical Working conditions: The working conditions should be safe, clean and hygienic. The work equipments should be updated and well-maintained.

e) **Status:** The employees' status within the organization should be familiar and retained.

f) **Interpersonal relations:** The relationship of the employees with his peers, superiors and subordinates should be appropriate and acceptable. There should be no conflict or humiliation element present.

g) **Job Security:** The organization must provide job security to the employees.

2) **Motivational factors-** According to Herzberg, the hygiene factors cannot be regarded as motivators. The motivational factors yield positive satisfaction. These factors are inherent to work. These factors motivate the employees for a superior performance.

These factors are called satisfiers. These are factors involved in performing the job. Employees find these factors intrinsically rewarding. The motivators symbolized the psychological needs that were perceived as an additional benefit. Motivational factors include:

a) **Recognition:** The employees should be praised and recognized for their accomplishments by the managers.

b) **Sense of achievement:** The employees must have a sense of achievement. This depends on the job. There must be a fruit of some sort in the job.

c) **Growth and promotional opportunities:** There must be growth and advancement opportunities in an organization to motivate the employees to perform well.

d) **Responsibility:** The employees must hold themselves responsible for the work. The managers should give them ownership of the work. They should minimize control but retain accountability.

e) **Meaningfulness of the work:** The work itself should be meaningful, interesting and challenging for the employee to perform and to get motivated.

This theory has relationship with the present paper because its deals with motivation. The relevance of the two-factor theory as related to this paper means that the managers of tertiary institutions must stress upon guaranteeing the adequacy of the hygiene factors to avoid employee dissatisfaction which is responsible for japa syndrome. Also, the managers and administrators of tertiary institutions must make sure they formulated policies and goals that is stimulating and rewarding so that the employees (academic staff) are motivated to work and stay in Nigeria carry out their functions. This theory emphasize upon job-enrichment so as to motivate the employees (academic staff). The job must utilize the employee's skills and competencies to the maximum. Focusing on the motivational factors can improve work-quality.

Reasons Why Academic Staff of Tertiary Institutions are Japaring

There are many factors responsible for japa syndrome in the Nigerian tertiary institutions. Some of these factors includes; poor salaries, poor work condition, economic problems, insecurity problems in Nigeria, inadequate infrastructure facilities and bad leadership.

Poor Salaries

Poor salaries of academic staff and non-academic staff of tertiary institutions is responsible for the Japa syndrome in the tertiary institutions. Academic staff of tertiary institutions are described by Ogunode, Kasimu, and Ibrahim (2023) as engine room of the tertiary institutions and their roles cannot be replaced. The academic staff are very important to the attainment of tertiary institutions goals. Another factor is for japa problem in the universities according to Aremu (2023) is poor remuneration, which is abysmally inhuman and disturbing. According to him, Nigerian academics are the worst paid globally, a development, he said, has driven lecturers out of the country in mass proportions. Poor salaries and condition of work are very crucial to the issues of shortage of lecturers (Offem, Anashie and Solomon 2018). Hassan as cited by Punch (2023) noted that most lecturers are traveling out of the country in pursuit of greener pastures. The salaries have not been increased for a long time. Another factor responsible for japa among academic staff of tertiary institutions is poor remuneration, which is abysmally inhuman and disturbing according to Oyesoji Aremu (2023). The main reason for this shortage of lecturers in the university system is usually poor remuneration. The take home salary is grossly inadequate compared to what is obtainable globally according to Nasir as cited by Ramalan, (2023). Victor, and Babatunde (2014) and Roy-Omonigho (2023) reaffirmed that lecturers are poorly paid in Nigeria. From the above, it can be affirm that poor salaries of Nigerian academic staff is a major factor propelling Japa syndrome in the tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

Poor work condition

Poor work condition which connote policies and social economic programme meant to be enjoyed by those working in the various tertiary institutions across the country. The welfare policies and allowance and work environment are not conducive in most tertiary institutions across Nigeria. Academic Staff Union of Universities, (ASUU) Federal University of Lafia (FULafia) as quoted by Dailytrust (2023) submitted that it is a fact that many lecturers have left the university system in Nigeria. This exodus is defined by the poor working conditions existing in the universities. Also, Onatolani as cited by Ramalan, (2023) identified poor welfare and poor working conditions as some factors responsible for the menace of Japa syndrome in the tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Supporting this view Egu, Ogbonna, Obike, & Obiuto, (2014); Aremu (2023) and Ogunode, Kasimu and Dahiru (2023) also blamed factors like poor working environment in many universities in Nigeria which has dampened the morale of many academics as prime cause of the mass exodus of academic staff from the various tertiary institutions across the country.

Economic problems

Another crucial factor causing the menace of Japa syndrome in the tertiary institutions in Nigeria is the harsh economic condition. Firstly, the removal of subsidy on the petroleum product by the new government that came to power in May, 2023. Secondly, the high rate of inflation in the country and the high unemployment rate among the youths. Dr Oluwagbemiga Adeleye, the chairman, ASUU, Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta (FUNAAB), blamed the shortage of lecturers on government policies and the bad economy. The terrible economic situation we have faced has made some lecturers seek greener pastures elsewhere around the world and that is what we call the

‘Japa’ syndrome,” he said. Onatolani as cited by Ramalan, (2023) also pointed to the inflation rate which is in its double digits, eating deep into the income of lecturers, which had remained static while expenses are increasing on a daily basis. Elazeh (2023) opined that in the midst of a high cost of living, shrinking opportunities for access to the basics of life, and dearth of jobs arising largely from leadership failure, hundreds of Nigerian youths are making frantic efforts to emigrate. He lamented that it is not only the unemployed youths that are making such moves. Professionals in critical sectors of the nation’s economy are also caught in this frenzy of mass exodus. Victor (2022) noted that Africa’s biggest economy is witnessing a massive distortion, with economic analysts worried that the ugly trends continue without much effort from the government. As a result, economic indicators seem very disturbing, especially inflation, unemployment, debt, subsidy payment and poverty rate. Rising inflation has raised the cost of living and pushed many into poverties. About 133 million Nigerians (63% of the population), are poor, as measured in multiple dimensions. Because over half of Nigeria's inflation is driven by rising food prices, many poor individuals and families face hunger. Persistent increase in unemployment is fueling insecurity, youth restiveness, low output and slow economic growth and a reduction in the standard of living of Nigerians. Underemployment is also very high at 22.8 per cent, while youth underemployment is 21.0 per cent. Nigeria’s debt profile has continued to rise since 2015.

Inadequate Infrastructure Facilities

Inadequate infrastructure facilities and unconducive work condition are some of the factors also causing the Japa syndrome in the tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Ogunode (2020) defined Infrastructure facilities as those facilities aiding delivery of academic and non-academic services in educational institutions. Infrastructural facilities include; libraries, laboratories, halls, offices, administrative blocks, hostels, roads facilities, water, electricity, internet etc. The availability of the infrastructural facilities in adequate quantities will support effective administration of educational institutions and the inadequacies will prevent effective administration of educational institutions. Availability of adequate Infrastructural facilities in tertiary institutions serve as a motivator factors and has capacity to retain staff. Everybody want a conducive work environment. It is unfortunate that most tertiary institutions across the country lacks adequate modern facilities for effective implementation of teaching, researching and provision of community services (Ebehikhalu & Dawam 2016). Oyeniran, (2023) cited Ojediran Ezenkiri, Mamman, Ezeani, & Francis (2021) and Ekundayo, & Kolawole, (2013) Aalso noted that lack of facilities across universities, poor funding and remunerations were some of the factors contributing to low morale and brain-drain in the education sector. Also, Elazeh (2023) and Chukwuemeka (2023) maintained that poor infrastructure, poor and sometimes delayed salaries and unpaid allowances are responsible for the mass resignation of lecturers.

Insecurity Problem

Insecurity problems in Nigeria and across the states also contributing to the problem of Japa syndrome among the academic staff in the tertiary institutions in Nigeria. In effect, Chukwuemeka (2023) opined that most Nigerians live in fear; fear of death, fear of losing properties etc. Not only does this pursue the dwellers of these communities but it also prevents

investors. Ogunode (2020) and Ogunode, and Abubakar (2021) noted that many students, lecturers and administrators have been killed while others kidnapped. The various attacks on the universities have resulted to school closure leading to unstable academic programme. *Ajayi (2023) described Nigeria as a country besieged with several issues such as insecurity, a crumbling economy with high inflation, weak human capital development, and dreadful governance. Insecurity is prevalent across the country, with every region vulnerable to the wave of violence. From the herdsmen on rampage in the country, majorly in the northern parts, to the unrest in south-eastern Nigeria, where whispers of secession have created tensions, Nigeria is in an unhealthy position security-wise. Kidnappings make daily news; bandit attacks on villages are commonplace; and highways have become breeding grounds for bloodshed. According to SBM Intelligence, a socioeconomic research firm, in 2021, more than 10,000 lives were lost in Nigeria due to actions of herdsmen, bandits, Boko Haram, and gang clashes. Ajayi (2023) concluded that the lack of belief that the country offers a chance to achieve one's goals and live a good life is at the centre of the mass emigration*

Bad leadership

Bad leadership styles of Nigerian leaders appear to be responsible for the Japa syndrome in the tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Nigeria leaders do not have interest in the development of education and other social infrastructure facilities that support economic development. Oludotun, (2023) lamented that Nigerian youths are frustrated with socio-economic challenges fuelled by unfulfilled government promises and bad leadership marked by absence of transparency and accountability. The situation brought about cold development, siphons scarce resources that could improve infrastructure and hinder education growth, public health and stack the deck against the poor masses.

Effects of Japa S yndrome on Tertiary Institutions Development in Nigeria

There are many effects of Japa syndrome in the tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Some of the effects includes; shortage of academic staff, poor quality of tertiary institutions, capital flight and slowing down tertiary institutions development

Shortage of academic staff

Shortage of academic staff in the tertiary institutions across Nigeria have been linked to the Japa syndrome in the tertiary institutions. Universities in Nigeria are battling a severe shortage of staff as thousands of lecturers leave the tertiary institutions to seek greener pastures in foreign lands. The Academic Staff Union of Universities branches in separate interviews with Punch (2023) confirmed that shortage of academic staff in most tertiary was due to the surge in the exit of the lecturers out of Nigeria and the concerns around the Integrated Personnel and Payroll Information System. ASUU at the Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, noted that about 100 lecturers had left the university, while the union at the Federal University, Gusau, Zamfara, disclosed that the institution was in need of about 1,000 lecturers to fill the vacancies created by those who had left. The union at the Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Ogun State said over 350 academic vacancies were available

at the institution, while 27 lecturers had left two faculties at the University of Lagos, as 100 workers at the University of Uyo travelled out of the country (Punch 2023). Ogunode, and Adamu (2021) confirmed shortage of academic staff in most Nigerian tertiary institutions.

Poor quality of tertiary institutions

The mass exodus of academic staff from the various tertiary institutions can lead to poor quality of tertiary education. According to Mamman, a former Vice Chancellor of Baze University, the brain drain phenomenon has a significant negative impact on universities in Nigeria. Mamman, lamented that when talented academics leave the country, it leaves a vacuum in the knowledge and expertise available to students and researchers. This, he said, negatively affects the quality of education, research, and innovation in Nigerian universities. “Instability causes so much damage to the system. You can’t plan, you cannot have international collaboration, students exchange. So the damage has been very huge and everybody recognises this including that we have some level of Japa in that sector. Academic Staff Union of Universities, (ASUU) Federal University of Lafia (FULafia) says the shortage of lecturers in Nigeria universities is affecting the standard and quality of education negatively. Ramalan, (2023) cited Olatunji the shortage of manpower is having negative impact on and teaching, research, and community service. Musa (2022) opined that government policies and nonchalant attitude to public university education in Nigeria, had affected the development of tertiary education in the country.

Increment in workload

The Japa syndrome that has plagued tertiary institutions in Nigeria can also lead high students-lecturers ratio which is not good for tertiary institutions development. . The Japa syndrome has led to reduction in the number of academic staff across the country. The reduction in the number of academic staff directly has led to an increased workload of the few lecturers available in the system. Recently, the Academic Staff Union of Universities, (ASUU) Federal University of Lafia (FULafia) noted that Universities lecturers who bear the brunt of the exit of their colleagues are also worried by the impact of this on their workload and academic standards. The universities are coping largely because the few existing lecturers are being over burdened with excess work load that are academic. “And in most departments, lecturers are made to teach large classes and more courses to be able to keep the courses running. The ASUU chairman observed that this has put undue pressure on their health of many lecturers leading to high mortality rates amongst lecturers in the university. Ramalan, (2023) noted that at the institutional level, the workload allocated to the available academic staff has simply increased; which means more responsibilities for the individual staff due to japa problem in the system. Olatunji, as cited by Ramalan, (2023) concluded that shortage of academic staff in many tertiary institutions have made lecturers to be overburdened with classes work as students population to continues to climb. This is evident in the lecturer to student ration in all the universities. In most cases you have a ratio of one lecturer to over 2,050 students.

Capital flight

The Japa syndrome among young Nigerian students seeking international education has led to huge capital flight. In July 2022, the Association of Nigerian Students in Europe revealed that Europe

alone has more than three million Nigerians enrolled in different higher institutions of learning. A survey also indicates that 89.87 per cent of Nigerian youths prefer to study in a university outside the country. Seventy three per cent of Nigerians, 60 per cent of doctors, and 89.87 per cent of students want to leave the country. The implication of foreign education on Nigerian economy is capital flight which has effect Naira. According to the CBN data gathered from amount spent on educational services under the sectoral utilisation for transactions valid for foreign exchange, a sum of \$375.99 million was released by the apex bank between June 2015 and December 2015. Further analysis of the data revealed that a total of \$269.1 million was released in 2016. There was a huge leap in 2017 when the apex bank disclosed that a total of \$514.16 was released for foreign education. In 2018, a total of \$546.78 was released (Tolu-kolawole 2022).

For 2019, there was a huge decrease as the bank released \$197.52 million. It was also noted that \$270.42 million was released in 2020 amidst the coronavirus pandemic. There was a huge leap in 2021 as the bank recorded a total of \$720.05 million released for same purpose. So far in 2022, only the data from January to August has been made available which revealed that a total of \$609.5 million has been released so far. The data from the apex bank revealed that Nigerians remitted more than \$3.5 billion to foreign academic institutions under former Buhari without significant reciprocity in the form of inflows from foreign sources to the local education sector. The huge net dollar outflows have dual adverse effects of underinvestment in domestic education and creates pressure on the naira exchange rate, economists said. The high demand for dollars to pay foreign educational institutions affects Nigeria's foreign reserves and contributes immensely to piling pressure on the exchange rate (Tolu-kolawole 2022). Lawal & Ogunode, (2021) noted that international education made by Nigerians is causing Nigeria a lot of capital flight which is affecting the economy.

Slowing down tertiary institutions development

The Japa syndrome among academic staff of tertiary institutions in Nigeria can hinder the development of tertiary education. For both the universities and varsity education, Elazeh (2023) observed it is a double whammy. While a sizeable number of lecturers sponsored by TETFund are not forthcoming, those within are resigning. Unfortunately, here we are, confronted by the sad reality that some Nigerian lecturers, having been sponsored by TETFund, either abscond outright or fail to complete the minimum of their bond before deciding to relocate. To say this 'japa' mentality smacks of dishonesty and sheer lack of patriotism is to say the least in the mildest way. Recently, TETFund Executive Secretary, Sunny Echono, lamented the spate of 'japa' among lecturers on the Fund's foreign scholarship, vowing that he will make the absconded refund money expended on them or be repatriated.

Tackling japa syndrome in Nigerian tertiary institutions

There many ways to tackle the Japa syndrome in Nigerian tertiary institutions. Some of the measures include increment of tertiary institutions budgetary allocation (Ifeyinwa and Okemute, 2023). Prof. Jeremiah Ojediran, Vice-Chancellor of Bells University of Technology, Ota, Ogun, was quoted by Oyeniran, (2023) appealed to the Federal Government to improve the funding of education, to reduce the "Japa Syndrome" in the country. Adetunji & Ogunleye, (2015); Nwafor,

Uchendu, & Akani, (2015); Ogunode, Lawan, & Solomon (2021); Ogunode, Attah, & Ebute (2023); Ogunode, Onyekachi, & Ayoko, (2023); Ogunode, Olaoye, & Yakubu (2023) concluded that the availability of funds plays a significant role in determining the provision of quality higher education. The quantity of funds made available during budgeting will go a long way in improving the quality of higher education in Nigeria. Adequate funding of tertiary education in Nigeria will lead to adequate funds in the various higher institutions' systems. This will help to ensure the effective administration and management of each institution. Higher institution managers will have access to adequate funds to implement the various programme of the institutions. Administrators of tertiary institutions will have enough money to spend on the provision of quality infrastructural facilities in various higher institutions.

Provision of modern infrastructure facilities. Government should provide more modern infrastructure facilities across the tertiary institutions. The provision of an enabling environment through improved remuneration and adequate facilities in the nation's universities, fewer Nigerians will travel out for greener pastures. The Federal Government needs to make education more attractive by increasing funding, providing new infrastructure and improving on the ready facilities in place, to boost research and publication (Daniel-Kalio, 2019; Ogunode and Jegede, 2021).

Government should review the salaries and allowance of academic staff. Dr. Sunmonu called for the improvement in remuneration and conducive environment as two key immediate issues the government should attend to for academics in tertiary institutions. Government should increase the salaries of workers so that they can compete favourably with their international counterparts. "Increasing the workers' salary is very imperative as what people outside earn as salary is 10 times more than what people are paid in Nigeria."

Provision of quality leadership to fix the various problems facing the economy. Provision of soft loans for farmers and private institutions to boost production to create jobs and reduce inflation. Investment on energy, roads and rails to aid effective distribution of agricultural products.

Increase investment in security sector and employ more security officers in all security agencies across the country. Reduce the rate of youth unemployment and provide social safety net for the unemployed to tackle insecurity challenges.

Finally, provision of conducive work environment, payment of withheld salaries, implementation of welfare policies and increment in research grant will help to curtail Japa syndrome in Nigerian tertiary institutions.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This paper discuss the effects of Japa' syndrome on the tertiary institutions development and measures to tackle the Japa' syndrome across the tertiary institutions. The paper identified factors responsible for Japa' syndrome among academic staff of tertiary institutions to includes; poor salaries, poor work condition, economic problems, insecurity problems in Nigeria, inadequate

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References

1. Adetunji, A. T., & Ogunleye, K. A. (2015) The effect of government policies on university administrators: A review of Nigeria. *Ge-International Journal of Management Research Administration & Leadership*.
2. Ajayi, A. (2023). Why many Nigerians are leaving the country <https://yourcommonwealth.org/social-development/why-many-nigerians-are-leaving-the-country/>
3. Agbajileke, O. (2023). Education minister blames 'Japa' as varsities face a dearth of lecturers. <https://guardian.ng/news/education-minister-blames-japa-as-varsities-face-a-dearth-of-lecturers/>
4. **Chukwuemeka E., S. (2023). Brain Drain in Nigeria: Causes, Effects & Solutions.** <https://bscholarly.com/brain-drain-nigeria/>
5. Daniel-Kalio, B. (2019). Policy Implementation and the Challenges of Leadership in Nigerian Universities. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Education*, 12(2), 326-350.
6. Ebehikhalu, N.O. & Dawam P. (2016) Inadequacy of Teaching and Learning Infrastructure: Reason Nigerian Universities cannot Drive Innovations. *Australian Journal of Education and Learning Research SCIE Journals*
7. Egu, H.N., Ogbonna, E. N. Obike, N. C. & Obiuto, C. C. (2014). Managing stress among lecturers in polytechnics of South Eastern, Nigeria. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5 (6): 333-338.
8. Ezenkiri, N, J., Mamman, H., Ezeani, U., D, Francis, T., T (2021). Academic Job: A Review on Stressors Among Teaching-Staff Of Tertiary Institutions. *SER*, 20 (1 & 2), 1-11
9. Ekundayo, H. T. & Kolawole, A. O. (2013). Stress among secondary school teachers in Ekiti State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Social Research*, 3 (2): 311-315.
10. Elazeh, M (2023). 'Japa' Syndrome and The TETFund Scholars. <https://leadership.ng/japa-syndrome-and-the-tetfund-scholars/>
11. Ifeyinwa F. M & Okemute, I., M (2023). Anambra State tertiary institutions: A Call For Urgent Reforms. *Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University Journal of Arts and Social Science Education (COOUJOASSE)* 3,(1), 1-10

12. Lawal, A & Ogunode, N,. (2021) Strike actions in Nigerian Higher Institutions: Meaning, Cause, Effects, achievement and way forward. *Scholarly publishing Discourse*, 1(1),17-30
13. Offem, O. O Anashie, A. I & Solomon, A A (2018) Effect Of Strikes On Management And Planning Of Educational Activities In Nigerian Universities. *Global Journal of Educational Research*, (17), 1-8
14. Nwafor, N. E. Uchendu, E. E. & Akani, C. O. (2015) Need for Adequate Funding in the Administration of Secondary Education in Nigeria. *Global Journal of Educational Research*, 14, 119-124
15. Ogunode, N.J, & Adamu, D.G. (2021) Shortage of Academic Staff in the Higher Institution of Learning in Nigeria. *Central Asian Journal of Social Sciences and History*, 2 (3), 109-123
16. Ogunode, N.J., Kasimu, S. & Ibrahim, I. (2023). Motivation and academic staff of Nigerian universities. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(7), 185–198,
17. Ogunode, N. J. (2020a). Administration of Public Universities in Nigeria: Problems and Solutions. *Journal Sinesthesia*, 10(2), 86-96
18. Ogunode, N. J. & Abubakar, L. (2021). Public Universities Administration in Nigeria: Challenges and the ways forward. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(11),26-38
19. Ogunode N,. J, Jegede, D & Abubakar M (2021) Problems Facing Academic Staff of Nigerian Universities and the Way Forward, *International Journal on Integrated Education*,4, (I), 230-24
20. Ogunode, N. J.,& Jegede, D. (2021). Evaluation of factors responsible for inadequate infrastructural facilities in public universities in north central Nigeria. *Intercathedra* 1(46), 43–50. <http://dx.doi.org/10.17306/J.INTERCATHEDRA.2021.00115>
21. Ogunode N,. J,. Kasimu , S,. & Dahiru, S. (2023). Analysis of Reasons for Abscondment of Sponsored Academic Staff. *AMERICAN Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies*, 01,(07),1-13
22. Ogunode N. J, Lawan, A.& Solomon, A. T (2021) Evaluation of Causes of Inadequate Funds in Nigerian Public Universities. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, (9), 93-103
23. Ogunode N. J, Olaoye, A. E & Yakubu, I. (2023) Adequate Funding of Public Universities and Effective Implementation of Core Curriculum and Minimum Academic Standards (CCMAS) in North-East, Nigeria Universities. *Analytical Journal of Education and Development*, 3(3), 215-222
24. Ogunode N. J, Onyekachi, C. M. & Ayoko, V. O. (2023) Investment in University Education in Nigeria: Obstacles and Possible Solutions. *Journal of Education, Ethics and Value* 2(1), 1-9.
25. Ogunode N. J, Attah, G. E. & Ebute, J. (2023) Investment in Education in Nigeria: Barriers and Way Forward. *European Journal of Higher Education and Academic Advancement* 1 (2), 61-71.

26. Oludotun, O. (2023).Nigerians and the japa syndrome. <https://punchng.com/nigerians-and-the-japa-syndrome/>
27. Oyeniran, A. (2023). Japa Wave: University Administrators Panic Over Exodus Of Academics. <https://independent.ng/japa-wave-university-administrators-panic-over-exodus-of-academics/>
28. Punch (2023) Lecturers shortage hits varsities, ASUU blames japa, IPPIS <https://punchng.com/lecturers-shortage-hits-varsities-asuu-blames-japa-ippis/>
29. Politics digest (2023).Japa Syndrome Hits Nigerian Universities As ASUU Decries Lecturer Shortage. <https://politicsdigest.ng/japa-syndrome-hits-nigerian/>
30. Ramalan, I. (2023).Japa syndrome: VCs, ASUU decry mass exodus of Nigerian lecturers, say ‘quality of university degrees in jeopardy’. <https://dailynigerian.com/japa-vcs-asuu-decry/>
31. Tolu-kolawole, D. (2022). CBN releases \$3.5bn for foreign education under Buhari. <https://punchng.com/cbn-releases-3-5bn-for-foreign-education-under-buhari/>
32. Roy-Omonigho, S, (2023). Poor remuneration, effects on university lecturers in Nigeria. <https://guardian.ng/opinion/poor-remuneration-effects-on-university-lecturers-in-nigeria/>
33. Tolu-Kolawole, D. (2023). Funding crisis weighs down public varsities, politicians float new institutions
34. <https://punchng.com/funding-crisis-weighs-down-public-varsities-politicians-float-new-institutions/> .
35. Victor, A.A. & Babatunde, E.G. (2014). Motivation and effective performance of academic staff in Higher Education (Case Study of Adekunle Ajasin University, Ondo State, Nigeria). *Online Submission, 1(2)*, 157-163.
36. Waheed, A (2023). ASUU Laments Exodus of Lecturers from Public Varsities https://leadership.ng/asuu-laments-exodus-of-lecturers-from-public-varsities/?utm_source